

THE USE OF REALIA TO IMPROVE YOUNG LEARNERS' VOCABULARY

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Abstract: Vocabulary is important in everyone's life for those who learn English as a second language. This is because if foreign language learners do not have enough vocabulary, it will significantly affect other language skills. This thesis contains opinions about the basics of using reality to improve the vocabulary of young students.

Key words: Realia, vocabulary, story, teaching strategies.

Introduction:

Vocabulary learning and teaching is a very important aspect of learning any foreign language. This is because the dictionary is the final decision in determining the level and knowledge of a foreign language learner. Having sufficient knowledge of vocabulary also plays an important role for the rest of the language skills, listening, speaking, reading and writing. Also, the necessary knowledge of vocabulary can turn a foreign language learner into an effective speaker, good listener, reader and writer. On the other hand, lack of vocabulary significantly affects these four language skills. Therefore, teaching and learning vocabulary needs special attention from teachers and students. Therefore, a systematic approach should be used to enrich students' vocabulary. This implies appropriate methodology, material and strategy by teachers. However, the success of any methodology, material and strategy is determined by the results in achieving the set goals and objectives. The common goal of any foreign language teaching and learning is to develop the competence of foreign language learners to communicate successfully, to be independent and independent.

For readers, this article analyzes the use of realism in the development of the vocabulary of English language learners, the development of their competencies, as well as the methodology of using short stories.

The term vocabulary refers to students' understanding of spoken and written words. The difference from this understanding is that the words that come out mean not only the dictionary definition, but also conceptual knowledge. And the acquisition of such knowledge is a construction process that takes place, as students connect with other words and learn examples over time, and learn to use words clearly in context. The words students need to master and their uses come in two forms: spoken and written. Spoken vocabulary

includes the words we hear and speak, and written vocabulary includes the words we read and write, and we recognize and use them. Another difference is based on word knowledge. Based on the knowledge of words, there can be receptive (receiver) and productive (effective) vocabulary. Receptive vocabulary includes words that we recognize when we hear or see them. On the other hand, effective vocabulary also includes these words. We use them when we speak or write. It is also argued and believed that our perception is greater than our effective vocabulary.

Learning and mastering the vocabulary of the target language plays a very important role in anything. It is very effective and important to conduct activities based on reality in the development of the vocabulary of students. Vocabulary knowledge allows the student to establish and achieve any main goal of successful communication, increase vocabulary, teach and learn foreign languages. Vocabulary knowledge also helps the learner discover the richness of that language through a variety of new words. Knowing the vocabulary helps the student to compare and contrast the foreign language and the mother tongue. It also helps to understand the linguistic systems of both languages through the similarities and differences between the two languages and learn the language in a real sense. In this sense, words are the main means of expression of the language and help the learner of a foreign language to communicate and express effectively. Mastery over vocabulary makes a student an effective speaker. The lack of vocabulary makes him fail to successfully organize and achieve communication. Having a low vocabulary can trap students in a vicious circle, as those who can't read extended texts have less success using vocabulary and word learning strategies. Therefore, students miss opportunities for expansion.

It is also important to develop students' vocabulary because in all other languages, lack of vocabulary affects other skills. Lack of vocabulary is also seen as one of the main reasons why students fail to communicate successfully, be it written or spoken. A lack of vocabulary is always noticeable in students with reading problems. Essential vocabulary through phonics helps students speak and write. A lack of vocabulary often leads to a lack of meaningful communication. Therefore, every effort is needed to improve students' vocabulary.

The importance of vocabulary in language pedagogy has always been recognized for everyone. Wilkins (1972), an early representative of the communicative approach, clearly showed that learning vocabulary is as important as learning grammar. A learner was judged on whether or not he or

she approached the level of a native speaker, based on whether he or she could use and pronounce collocations well. Teaching, development and learning should be the main concern in the classroom. Vocabulary is one of the most important parts of language acquisition. Therefore, learning new words consciously and unconsciously is the main basis for the future development of students' language level. Thus, teachers should try to develop students' vocabulary and help their communicative development.

Methods and strategies to develop students' vocabulary based on realia:

Traditionally, vocabulary was not a separate subject for students to study, but was taught in speaking, listening, reading and writing lessons. During the lesson, students use their own vocabulary related to classroom activities provided by the teacher and classmates and learn new words. For many students, learning vocabulary means learning a list of new words with meanings in their native language without real context practice. In most cases, the educational context, students, often have to deal with an unfamiliar word while learning their language. During such an encounter with a new word, students look up the meaning of the word in a bilingual dictionary. Often they write new words without any idea of their actual use in context.

Many scholars have stopped learning vocabulary by memorizing new words. This is because the vocabulary often leads to the neglect of the lexical aspect and is learned in this way. In other words, students know how to use vocabulary in a specific way, but they don't know how to use it in real-life communication with different meanings.

There are a variety of other strategies and approaches used by teachers to develop vocabulary for students.

First, knowledge of words can be acquired incidentally, where vocabulary develops through immersion in language activities. Vocabulary is taught through direct instruction, where students can also learn vocabulary through a structured approach. Teachers can also promote the use of vocabulary research, dictionaries, thesauruses, and spelling.

Teachers can also give their students a vocabulary notebook where they can write down unfamiliar or new words. Even playing word games can be encouraged. Interactive worksheets can be created, displayed, and students can learn new, interesting, and unusual vocabulary. As an example, Michael Graves (2006) provides a framework for successful vocabulary programs that support students' vocabulary development and effective teaching. At the heart of his teaching is a four-part program approach to developing strong vocabulary:

- (1) providing enrichment and diverse language experiences,
- (2) teaching individual words,
- (3) strategies for teaching word learning;
- (4) education of word consciousness.

But more importantly, teachers themselves can help students develop and enrich their vocabulary as an experience, which can develop and expand independent reading.

Conclusion:

In short, the lack of vocabulary among students causes various difficulties for them in the process of communication. Therefore, carefully planned vocabulary instruction, especially the use of short stories, is necessary to overcome the most common problems students face.

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